

PUBLIC ACCESS

© GENOMED4ALL 2021-2024

GENOMED4ALL

D2.4

2nd Report of the Ethics Advisory Board

GENOMED4ALL receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101017549

GENOMED4ALL

Genomics for Next Generation Healthcare

D2.4

2nd Report of the Ethics Advisory Board

Revision **v1.0**

Work package	WP2
Task	TX.X
Due date	31-12-2022
Submission date	31-12-2022
Deliverable lead	i~HD
Version	V1.0
Authors	Nathan Lea and Dipak Kalra
Reviewers	Nikolaus Forgó (External – University of Vienna, EAB Chair), Mahsa Shabani (External, Ghent University, EAB Member), Paul Timmers (External – University of Oxford, EAB Member), Rosa Sánchez Puga (Internal, UPM)

Abstract

Deliverable 2.4 provides the second report of the GenoMed4All Ethical Advisory Board (EAB). This report has been compiled after the first meeting of the Ethical Advisory Board held on 19th January 2022, and a subsequent set of meetings in November 2022.

Following the completion of the previous meeting and submission of D2.2, GenoMed4All focused its efforts on developing the mapping and ethical principles identified in the previous meeting, but had to address as a priority the changing expectations around GDPR compliance

and development of the data sharing agreements. Identification of the roles of GenoMed4All partners had to be prioritised, and a new Joint Controller Agreement Template had to be agreed by the partners. This underpinned the compliance requirements that were being overseen by the EAB. Due to regulatory changes and evolved interpretations in several jurisdictions, including France and Italy respectively, the agreements and approaches had to be updated.

A set of new Joint Controller Agreement has therefore been drafted, one for each Use Case. In addition to this, the mappings for the regulatory compliance have also been developed, and ethical principles adhered to by the project partners. There has been a fundamental shift in terms of data sharing, where the previous step of sharing anonymised or pseudonymised data has been replaced by a federated learning approach where data does not leave the clinical or registry sites, rather the algorithms are trained within their zone of control and the trained algorithms are the only materials being shared centrally to the repository.

The EAB Members were updated individually due to difficulties in scheduling a plenary meeting. Each have provided feedback on the developments and have reviewed this deliverable.

Just prior to the submission of this Deliverable Mahsa Shabani had to stand down from the EAB due to other commitments. A new member will be approached early in 2023. Additionally the WP1 Lead and Project Coordinator, Annelore Hermann, moved to a new position, as did Francesco Cremonesi. Rosa Sánchez Puga has been appointed Project Manager and Administrator. Federico Alvarez is now the WP1 Lead.

Keywords

Ethics, data protection, governance, advisory board, risk management.

Document revision history

Version	Date	Description of change	Contributor(s)
v0.5	01-12-2022	1 st version of the report for WP2 Leads' comment	Nathan Lea (i~HD), Dipak Kalra (i~HD)
V0.9	02/12/2022	Version for EAB Chair's review	Nikolaus Forgó
V1.0	05/12/2022	Candidate Final Version for EAB Review	Mahsa Shabani (External, Ghent University, EAB Member), Paul Timmers (External – University of Oxford, EAB Member), Rosa Sánchez Puga (Internal, UPM)
V1.1	19/12/2022	Final Draft for Submission incorporating changes from reviewers	Nathan Lea (Internal, i~HD)

Disclaimer

The information, documentation and figures available in this deliverable are provided by the GENOMED4ALL project's consortium under EC grant agreement **101017549** and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Copyright notice

© GENOMED4ALL 2021-2024

Project co-funded by the European Commission in the H2020 Programme

Nature of the deliverable

R

Dissemination level

PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

CO Confidential to GENOMED4ALL project and Commission Services

* Deliverable types:

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

Table of contents

1	Executive summary	7
2	Introduction	9
2.1	Development of GenoMed4All and Updates	9
2.2	Structure of this report	10
3	Matters Arising Since the First EAB Meeting	10
3.1	Project Developments: EAB Constitution	10
3.2	Project Developments: Identification of Partner GDPR Roles and Updates to Joint Controller Agreements.....	10
3.3	Project Developments: From Data Sharing to Federated Learning.....	11
3.4	Regulatory and European Developments.....	11
4	Update on Action Items from Last EAB	12
4.1	Ethics and Governance Mapping	12
4.2	Engagement with Project Partners around Applying Ethical Principles.....	13
4.3	Applying European Commission Toolkits for Risk Assessments	14
5	Conclusions	14

Abbreviations

HDs	Haematological diseases
FL	Federated Learning
NN	Neural Network
MDS	Myelodysplastic Syndromes
MM	Multiple Myeloma
SCD	Sickle Cell Disease
WP	Workpackage
EAB	Ethical Advisory Board
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DMP	Data Management Plan
JCA	Joint Controller Agreement

1 Executive summary

Deliverable 2.4 provides the second report of the GenoMed4All Ethical Advisory Board (EAB). This report has been compiled after the first meeting of the Ethical Advisory Board held on 19th January 2022 and a series of subsequent meetings with each of the EAB members throughout November 2022

The EAB members were presented with the updated position with regards the project objectives and progress, the data protection and ethics oversight and assessments for the project. Following the completion of the previous meeting and submission of D2.2, GenoMed4All focused its efforts on developing the mapping and ethical principles identified in the previous meeting, but had to address as a priority the changing expectations around GDPR compliance and development of the data sharing agreements.

Identification of the roles of GenoMed4All partners had to be prioritised, and a new Joint Controller Agreement Template had to be agreed by the partners. This underpinned the compliance requirements that were being overseen by the EAB. Due to regulatory changes and evolved interpretations in several jurisdictions, including France and Italy respectively, the agreements and approaches had to be updated.

A set of new Joint Controller Agreement has therefore been drafted, one for each Use Case. They are near finalisation and are available in D2.3. In addition to this, the mappings for the regulatory compliance have also been developed, and ethical principles adhered to by the project partners. The mappings are available as an annex to this deliverable.

There has been a fundamental shift in terms of data sharing within the project as a result of evolving regulatory expectations; new legislation around the conduct of registries at Member State level created additional challenges for the data provider sites, particularly in France and Italy. The previous approach of sharing anonymised or pseudonymised data centrally within GenoMed4All has been replaced by a federated learning approach across the consortium for each Use Case where data does not leave the clinical or registry sites, rather the algorithms are trained within their zone of control and the trained algorithms are the only materials being shared centrally to the repository.

In addition to this, the enactment of several EU Regulations including the Data Governance Act, development of the Artificial Intelligence Act has required GenoMed4All to consider the documentation and approach specifications with an additional degree of diligence. This coupled with the development of the European Health Data Space has emphasised the need for additional monitoring by regulatory experts within GenoMed4All.

The EAB Members were broadly satisfied with the developments and were sympathetic to the evolving regulatory space. They welcomed the shift to a federated learning approach and sharing

trained algorithms only to a central repository. They were mindful of the challenges faced by data providers in light of new regulations at local Member State Level.

One member of the EAB, Mahsa Shabani, has had to stand down due to other commitments. A replacement member will be approached in early 2023. Additionally the WP1 Lead and Project Coordinator, Annelore Hermann, moved to a new position, as did Francesco Cremonesi. Rosa Sánchez Puga has been appointed Project Manager and Administrator. Federico Alvarez is now the WP1 Lead.

2 Introduction

This Deliverable 2.4 provides the second report of the GenoMed4All Ethical Advisory Board (EAB). The EAB has been constituted by inviting three independent experts in the area of advanced techniques for using health data to improve outcomes and foster digital innovation. The EAB goal is to provide an independent view on the ethical robustness of the project and its activities across the consortium partners with specific focus on its protection of data and ethical AI development. For the second report, the EAB has considered updates and developments relating to ethical and regulatory requirements for GenoMed4All in line with their role as defined in Deliverable 2.2, the first report of the EAB.

2.1 Development of GenoMed4All and Updates

After the first meeting of the EAB on 19th January 2022, GenoMed4All addressed the need to install a data sharing agreement between project partners. Throughout the early part of 2022, the role of each partner had to be reviewed carefully.

Further details are available in D2.3, which includes the data sharing agreements and description of the approach taken to develop them, where the descriptions are provided of the approaches taken to develop them. There is a brief summary in section three below.

There have been regulatory changes at Member State level that have had implications for the governance of GenoMed4All and development of governance materials like data sharing agreements. As a result of this and after careful consideration, GenoMed4All decided to make the first phase of the project a federated learning approach like the second phase as opposed to sharing data across partners centrally and across borders. This allayed many of the security and ethical concerns that had been raised throughout the project.

Additionally developments with the Data Governance and Artificial Intelligence Acts and the European Health Data Space, has compelled GenoMed4All to consider its approaches in line with these developments.

These matters have been developing in line with the action items that were identified at the last EAB meeting in January 2022. These were as follows and their development are described in section 4:

1. Development of a comprehensive mapping of the existing and prospective ethical approvals across the project combined with the data dictionaries, data processing, outputs and activities for each of the partners.
2. Efforts to engage with the project and develop a series of core ethical principles that could underpin and reinforce agreements made between project partners as well as those of with parties, both public and industrial, outside the consortium.
3. Apply the recent European Commission toolkits for assessing risks relating to Artificial Intelligence development and use to address the specific issues GenoMed4All has encountered.

2.2 Structure of this report

This report describes in Section 3 the matters that arose since the last EAB meeting including personnel changes and those which have had an impact on the regulatory compliance matters that are before the EAB. Section 4 updates on the action items from the last EAB and next steps.

The report concludes with proposed next steps and the next meeting of the EAB.

3 Matters Arising Since the First EAB Meeting

There have been several project related and wider regulatory and pan European developments that are described in this section.

3.1 Project Developments: EAB Constitution

Since the first EAB meeting there have been some personnel developments. Annelore Hermann of UPM, WP1 Lead and Project Administration Officer. Francesco Cremonesi also left for another role. Rosa Sánchez Puga has been appointed Project Manager and Administrator. Federico Alvarez is now WP1 Lead. In late November 2022, Mahsa Shabani had to stand down from her role on the EAB due to other commitments. A replacement will be approached in early 2023.

The members of the EAB are therefore now as follows (in alphabetical order):

- ❑ **Federico Álvarez (UPM, WP1 Lead and Project Co-ordinator, Internal)**
- ❑ **Tommaso Foglia (DataWizard, WP2 Member, Internal)**
- ❑ **Nikolaus Forgó (External EAB Member, Professor of IT and IP Law, University of Vienna, External)**
- ❑ **Dipak Kalra (i~HD, WP2 Lead, Internal)**
- ❑ **Nathan Lea (i~HD, WP2 Lead, Internal)**
- ❑ **Anna Rizzo (Data Wizard, WP2 Member, Internal)**
- ❑ **Paul Timmers (External EAB Member, Research Associate University of Oxford, Former EU Director European Commission, External)**

A plenary meeting could not be held due to scheduling conflicts for the EAB Members. Nathan Lea and Anna Rizzo therefore updated each member of the EAB individually throughout November and provided updates as detailed in this report.

3.2 Project Developments: Identification of Partner GDPR Roles and Updates to Joint Controller Agreements

Since January 2022, following the Data Protection by Design and Default approach, WP2 continued to develop the understanding of and compliance with GDPR and wider ethical principles. This culminated in the conclusion that project partners would be Joint Controllers except where they were only providing infrastructure and software, where they would be Data Processors or Sub-Processors.

With due regard to the EAB oversight and conclusions a Joint Controller Agreement based on the European Commission Joint Controller Templates for consortia were developed for each Use Case and have been reviewed by the legal teams for each partner. A full discussion of this approach is available in Deliverable 2.3, including drafts of the JCAs themselves.

The JCAs are nearing completion and are due for signature shortly. They have however been subject to update as a result of the decision to move to a fully federated learning approach for the project as part of validation work as phase one of the project.

3.3 Project Developments: From Data Sharing to Federated Learning

As the project developed, the technical and data provider partners decided that the sharing of anonymous or pseudonymised data should be replaced by taking on a federated learning approach instead. This helped to minimise risks to participants as data would no longer leave the data provider sites and that algorithm training could occur locally as opposed to centrally. The only materials that would be shared centrally would be the trained algorithms themselves.

The approach is now therefore to develop the algorithms within the infrastructures and do continual evaluations on synthetic data. The algorithms could then be shared with the data provider sites and trained there. Once training cycles were completed, the algorithms could be brought back to the developer areas and tested against the synthetic data. This is the approach that will be taken throughout 2023 as the algorithms are developed.

This change in approach has therefore provided additional assurance around participant protection but has also helped to allay some of the regulatory developments and concerns that have arisen as a result with some data providers.

3.4 Regulatory and European Developments

Several significant EU wide Regulations have either been enacted or are being drafted and consulted on. These include the Data Governance Act that has been enacted, the Data Act that is near enactment, the AI Act that is being drafted and is expected to be enacted in early 2025 and the European Health Data Space, which is due for enactment in late 2024.

Each of these Regulations are to be read alongside GDPR, but make provision for a variety of new or existing mechanisms, including the role of data intermediaries, provision for altruism around data sharing, assurance mechanisms for the safety and security of AI, and standards and approaches for health care delivery and secondary health data use, prioritising the interoperability of health data systems and adherence to the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable Principles.

In parallel to this there have been new legislative instruments across Europe about the sharing of health data, particularly for health registries, and stricter interpretations of existing GDPR provisions.

This has partially informed the decisions around avoiding sharing data across GenoMed4All, rather encouraging the federated learning approach as described in the previous section. This also has implications for the ethical principles under consideration by GenoMed4All.

This has also had the knock on effect of requiring more detailed JCA development negotiations with partners and some redrafting, as well as putting the consideration of ethical principles in a new light, especially as GenoMed4All shifts to a fully federated learning model, as discussed in the next section.

4 Update on Action Items from Last EAB

The three main action items from the January 2022 EAB meeting are discussed in this section. It should be noted that prioritisation has shifted from a couple of the points to attend to the GDPR compliance matters via the work for the JCA. This was also in light of changes to the federated learning approach and the regulatory changes described in the last section.

4.1 Ethics and Governance Mapping

The action item from January 2022 was: *Development of a comprehensive mapping of the existing and prospective ethical approvals across the project combined with the data dictionaries, data processing, outputs and activities for each of the partners.*

This mapping is provided below as a template and provides a basis to populate the details as the project develops.

The premise for this mapping is to be able to record the activity and the responsibility of each of the partners involved for each of the Use Cases. It can provide a clear description of the particulars around handling data for the research as encapsulated by each use case.

The information gathered can then be much more clearly provided for regulatory oversight and submission. This is particularly important for adherence to the likely drafting of the AI Act, which places an emphasis on independent certification by competent authorities where safety critical systems, such as those related to risk prediction and intervention during health care.

4.2 Engagement with Project Partners around Applying Ethical Principles

This action item from the January meeting stated: *Efforts to engage with the project and develop a series of core ethical principles that could underpin and reinforce agreements made between project partners as well as those of with parties, both public and industrial, outside the consortium.*

Addressing this action item took on a pragmatic approach that is still ongoing. Part of the engagement was compelled by the need to draft the JCAs between partners and identify the GDPR roles. This entailed clarification of the Joint Controllership for the project, as well as identifying infrastructure partners as Data Processors and not Controllers.

These discussions within the project partnership were led by the GDPR compliance requirements but also by the basis of existing ethical approvals, the presence or need for informed consent and the concerns from data providers around regulatory changes as discussed.

As a result of these discussions and other key developments, the decision was reached by GenoMed4All to exclude the need for data sharing and conduct the training of algorithms at the data provider facilities in all cases as described in Section 3.

The learning from the engagement has provided a means to recommend the following possible ethical principles:

- ❑ Where possible, ensure that data transfers are minimised to protect the rights and interests of participants. This shall not introduce risk of bias, error or quality degradation in the algorithm development, where sharing of training data must occur if there could be a significant risk.
- ❑ Make use of synthetic data where possible, mindful that algorithms must be validated on real data to be better assured as to accuracy and value.
- ❑ The use of identifiable data or is anonymisation or pseudonymisation either for training or in cases where sharing is required must occur within the bounds of existing consent and Independent Review Board Opinions. Where consent is not possible, an IRB view must be sought for a view on whether this is appropriate.

4.3 Applying European Commission Toolkits for Risk Assessments

The action item for 2022 was *Apply the recent European Commission toolkits for assessing risks relating to Artificial Intelligence development and use to address the specific issues GenoMed4All has encountered.*

Given the change in focus from a centralised to a federated training model, it is advisable that these assessments are applied after the development work is better established and piloting can commence. This should be possible by July 2023, though it should be noted that the toolkits remain in draft form and may not be finalised by July 2023.

5 Conclusions

GenoMed4All has advanced in its delivery since the last EAB meeting in January 2022. It has seen development in the understanding of its required data flows and adherence to ethical considerations as the regulatory and societal expectations contexts have advanced.

The project has therefore adapted to these new challenges by taking an approach to avoid sharing personal or de-identified data centrally, conduct training locally within data provider sites and share only the trained algorithms for validation and eventual testing.

This approach honours the spirit of the regulatory instruments and the approvals, and respects the consents for participants in both the retrospective and prospective use cases. The approach enhances the protections without compromising the quality of the efforts.

Three guiding ethical principles have been proposed and will be offered to the GenoMed4All partners for additional review. The next EAB meeting should occur by June 2023.

GENOMED 4ALL

genomed4all.eu

 @genomed4all

 /genomed4all

GENOMED4ALL receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101017549